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Open Science Badges, Awards and Prizes: a German Perspective in the Context of the Sustainable Development Goals

Abstract: Open science is relevant to all Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), in particular SDG 16 to “Promote just, peaceful and inclusive societies”, and to various targets of SDG 4, Quality education. Open science badges, prizes and awards for (and by) libraries and librarians evaluate and recognise open science and open access practices and provide an opportunity to present related activities to the outside world in a condensed form. As a rule, the focus is not on mundane self-promotion, but rather on the goal of external and internal reflection and promotion of the work done, as well as better presentation of the open resources and workflows produced. It is also a stimulus for education and exchange – both within the institution, with the professional public and with the institution’s users. This article provides an overview of the various badges, awards and prizes relevant to Germany as incentive systems for open science and open access activities, and describes their criteria, application procedures and benefits. In addition, two further examples are presented that could serve as models and have potential for wider adoption in the open science community. The chapter concludes with recommendations for improvement and future design of badges, awards and prizes.

Keywords: Open Science; Open Scholarship; Open Educational Resources; Badges; Awards; Prizes; Rewards

Introduction

Libraries play important roles in the field of open science. From a researcher's perspective, libraries are primarily open science service providers, advocates/educators, policy makers and knowledge producers (Liu and Liu 2023, 9). Other roles include promoters for example of research diversity, evaluators of resources and mediators/advisors (Tzanova 2020, 291–295).

The more information is available and made accessible via open access, open data and open educational resources, the more important the specific role of educators becomes. This applies in particular to education for sustainable development: “Educators re-

main key actors in facilitating learners' transition to sustainable ways of life, in an age where information is available everywhere [...]" (UNESCO 2020a, 30).

Education goes hand in hand with promoting the topic and raising awareness. "Being strong advocates for Open Access, academic libraries contribute to releasing the research potential of digital technologies and communications by promoting openness [...]" (Tzanova 2020, 291).

A suitable framework for activities is the UNESCO Recommendation on open science: "UNESCO is, itself, committed to making open access and open data one of the central supporting agendas for achieving the Sustainable Development Goals" (UNESCO 2015, 8). The core tasks and objectives of the UNESCO Recommendation on open science include for example "investing in human resources, training, education, digital literacy and capacity building for open science" (UNESCO 2021b, 26) and "fostering a culture of open science and aligning incentives for open science" (UNESCO 2021b, 27).

The recommendations highlight the necessity to create funding and other incentive mechanisms to publicise, promote and strengthen open science (UNESCO 2021b, 32). Badges, awards and prizes are a suitable and powerful tool, as they are based on clear criteria, recognise joint efforts, present best practices, create public recognition, and, above all, represent a real reward. "Politicians and research managers use to speak about carrots and sticks, a combination of reward and punishment to induce the desired open science behaviour. Behavioural psychologists know that generally, reward is more efficient for positive reinforcement than punishment. [...] It may work; but it is not helpful to promote [...] open science as a positive value and objective" (Schöpfel and Azeroual 2021, 449).

In the following, the connections between SDGs, education for sustainable development (ESD), open science, the contributions of libraries and, of course, specific open science badges, awards and prizes, which are particularly relevant for or of interest in Germany, are put into a closer causal context.

Context

Contextualising the Role of Open Science in Attaining the SDGs

Various studies and articles describe how open science or approaches integrated into open science (open access, open educational

resources) support, accelerate or even enable the achievement of the SDGs.

In a two-page table, Mamtora and Pandey (2018, 6-7) describe the contribution of open access to each of the seventeen SDGs. Access to relevant research results and data and the corresponding facilitation of learning are relevant for almost every goal. In some cases, the development of policies and projects in the target context, collaborations, and the reporting of progress on the basis of accessible data and information for individual SDGs are also mentioned. The same applies to the promotion of awareness-raising. In addition to open access, Mamtora and Pandey also consider open data to be essential (Mamtora and Pandey 2018, 6–8). They clearly summarise, “the more freely accessible the information is, without the worry of having to find the funds to acquire the document, the more the likelihood of it being used to solve a problem, and for it to lead towards the successful attainment of a particular goal” (Mamtora and Pandey 2018, 3).

Muth and Salvador Lopez (2021) take a more specific look at individual SDGs. For example, open access is primarily of essential importance for SDG 16, Peace, justice and strong institutions, in particular for its target 10 to ensure public access to information and protect fundamental freedom. However, it is also essential in the context of SDG 9, Industry, innovation and infrastructure, to foster innovation, for example through the possibilities of machine processing of open data, improved knowledge transfer in business and society and thus better decision-making by companies, also with regard to sustainable products and services. In the context of SDG 10, Reduced inequalities, to reduce inequality within and among countries, open access helps to reduce financial inequality, especially the global gap between North and South in access to research information. With regard to the SDG 4, Quality education, to ensure inclusive and quality education for all and promote lifelong learning, open access (OA) empowers all interested parties to educate themselves on specific topics. “OA democratises the world of learning in which research information is not only available for the academic elites” (Muth and Salvador Lopez 2021). This also benefits political decision-makers, committed volunteers, companies and non-governmental organisations engaged in sustainable development.

Camkin et al. (2022) also emphasise the current unequal access to reliable information. “Achieving the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals is increasingly challenging due to widening

inequality in access to scientific and technological knowledge and resources. [...] Acknowledging that open science can be a powerful tool to reduce inequalities, UNESCO has been supporting the shift to open science. Following global multistakeholder consultation, the UNESCO Recommendation on open science was adopted” (Camkin et al. 2022, 1). An important goal of the recommendations is to gain “open scientific knowledge. [...] In open scientific knowledge, users gain free access to scientific publications, open research data, open education resources, open source, and open hardware” (Camkin et al. 2022, 5).

Contextualising the Role of Open Science in the ESD Programme

Similar to open science as stated above, the UNESCO Education for Sustainable Development (ESD) programme contributes to the achievement of each of the seventeen SDGs:

- “ESD raises the awareness of the 17 goals in education settings: ESD enhances the understanding of learners and the general public on what the SDGs are [...].
- ESD promotes critical and contextualized understanding of the SDGs: [...] ESD raises questions on the inter-linkages and tensions between different SDGs and provides learners with the opportunity to navigate the required balancing acts with its holistic and transformational approaches.
- ESD mobilizes action towards the achievement of the SDGs: [...] These efforts continue to mobilize action for sustainable development in education settings [...] (UNESCO 2020a, 16).

The ESD programme is particularly important for SDG 4, Quality education (UNESCO 2020a, 60): “Open Educational Resources (OER) can support quality education that is equitable, inclusive, open and participatory as well as enhance academic freedom and professional autonomy of teachers by widening the scope of materials available for teaching and learning” (UNESCO 2020b, 4).

Open access and, in particular, open educational resources (OER) as part of open science are recognized in the new ESD programme *Education for Sustainable Development: Towards achieving the SDGs (ESD for 2030)*. ESD for 2030 was launched at an international conference “Learn for our Planet. Act for Sustainability” organised by UNESCO and supported by the German Govern-

ment. The book *German OER Practices and Policy* states, “a commonly shared motive for OER is that the knowledge society requires open access to knowledge and free sharing of this knowledge” (Orr, Neumann, and Muuss-Merholz 2017, 31). OER are also “seen as motor for more open learning scenarios” and “as a solution to licensing problems in the use of learning materials from third parties” (Orr, Neumann, and Muuss-Merholz 2017, 31).

Ossiannilsson concludes, “open education, OER, and parallel movements, such as open science, open innovation, next-generation empowerment, open communication, open partnerships, and open ecosystems, will be catalysts for systemic change toward a new social contract and knowledge-based action to transform education for global sustainability” (Ossiannilsson 2023, 558).

Contextualising the Role and Contribution of Libraries

Libraries can be positioned in the aforementioned contexts as follows. The roles described in the context of open science can also be largely transferred to commitments, activities and other contributions to achieving the SDGs and, as part of this, target-oriented SDG education within the ESD programme. See in more detail Fig. 1:

Fig. 1: Roles and contributions of libraries to open science and SDGs. Figure created by the authors.

Each role overlaps with the others. For example, creating open access to information, data and resources, also in the context of achieving the SDGs, is one of the core tasks of libraries in their role as service providers. But this can also be supported in their role as publishers or knowledge producers, for example in the case of library-operated university presses, repositories or OJS/OMP instances. As publishers or knowledge producers, they can for example “aspire to develop sustainable practices and act as champions of the SDGs [...], publishing books and journals that will help inform, develop, and inspire action in that direction” (United Nations 2024b). In addition, the access possibilities must be communicated, explained and promoted in the role of an educator, advocate and mediator or advisor. In the role of assessor of resources, critical or problematic sources, such as those from predatory publishers, are pointed out. At the same time, the diverse research materials on SDGs (open data, methodology descriptions for data collection and studies, publications, teaching and educational materials) and approaches from different disciplines can be curated, processed and presented by libraries and their subject specialists. This is where the role of the promoter of research diversity is evident. Further library roles can also be applicable in some cases. For example, openly accessible information can contribute to policy development and target achievement monitoring: “Libraries support dissemination of information and research to help decision makers achieve the SDGs” (United Nations 2024a). They can also act as autonomous policy makers by formulating policies to promote SDG-related and open science practices in their publishing and knowledge producing activities, when funding costs via library-managed publication funds or when negotiating subscription contracts such as publish-and-read agreements.

The contributions of libraries to both open science and the achievement of the SDG targets are grouped together around Fig. 1. In addition to the technical and service-related provision of open access to information, they offer data and learning materials and support for universal information literacy (for example through curricular support, but also by opening up to citizens and supporting lifelong learning, including disadvantaged groups and the disabled through digital inclusion). Libraries can also raise awareness and promote open science and SDGs through community engagement with partnerships and the identification or creation of incentives. Other contributions can be creating diversity by offering open educational resources in various languages and from several scientific disciplines and supporting policy developments, projects and monitoring measures (Ekpolomo 2023; IFLA 2024; Mamtora and Pandey

2018, 6–7; Mashroofa 2022, 52–54; Muth and Salvador Lopez 2021).

Contextualising the Role of Badges, Awards and Prizes

The wide range of activities of open science and open access actors, particularly those based in, or supported and influenced by, libraries, and the open resources they have created or enhanced for quality education are often not yet perceived and appreciated as they should be, given their societal and global impact over the past decade. Projects that aim to change this include open science and open access badges, prizes and awards. They assess a wide range of criteria for open science and open access activities and offer the possibility to promote these activities in an award-worthy and condensed form.

They are therefore mentioned by the European Commission as one general measure of relevant incentives and rewards alongside, for example, training to achieve best open practices:

- “Improved training and support for research dissemination [...]
- Visible recognition of open science activities (including Citizen Science and open Education), used widely to enhance reputation and credibility [...], establishment of open science prizes, and encouraging champions and role models” (Miedema et al. 2018, 30)

In some cases, the development of such open science prizes can already be seen in the national action plans of European countries, which is recommended by the European Commission to incentivise open science (Miedema et al. 2018, 112). “The French National Plan for open science requires in a general way that the assessment system for researchers and research institutions must be updated to reflect the principles and practices of open science [...]; it also announces a “research data award” [...]. The purpose is clearly stated: the development of open science [...] through incentives and rewards” (Schöpfel and Azeroual 2021, 447). Finland awards several open science and open education prizes as part of the Finnish open science and Research Roadmap (Secretariat for the National open science and Research Coordination, Federation of Finnish Learned Societies 2023).

Awards and education are therefore two valuable pillars of open science (Liu and Liu 2023, 1) and, as shown in the context of Fig. 1, also of the SDGs in the context of ESD. In addition to the

benefits of clear criteria and targets, assessment, recognition and promotion, it should be emphasised that they indeed represent a “real” reward. “Rewarding and incentivizing require a clearly defined target behavior. [...] Some of the most often suggested incentives (tenure, promotion, funding) are no real rewards – they already exist and [...] just add new conditions to get them. More sticks than carrots, in some way” (Schöpfel and Azeroual 2021, 449).

Definitional Differences Between Badges, Awards and Prizes

An award is usually an honour for outstanding achievements in a specific field. The award does not have to represent a winner in a competition, but can in some cases be achieved simply through participation and achievement, in the sense of achieving certain criteria. This also sometimes distinguishes awards from prizes, as prizes are often part of a competitive effort and associated with monetary rewards (Gallus and Frey 2016, 1701).

A badge, presented or displayed upon receipt, also represents a special achievement and is often used as a motivator of behaviour, a signifier, a credential, or a pedagogical tool. In the digital and educational sectors, badges are used as evidence of completed learning pathways, achievements or special skills (Ahn, Pellicone, and Butler 2014, 3-4). Digital badges are validated indicators and commonly contain digital information about the assessment, evidence and other metadata required for the badge. Badges are designed to encourage the sharing of knowledge and resources, create evidence-based transparency about assessments, and provide recognition (Petriashvili et al. 2020, 6-8).

Further Positive Effects of Badges, Awards, and Prizes and their Relationship to Certifications

When badges, awards and prizes are granted on the basis of a transparent catalogue of criteria, there is a close connection and overlap with certifications. Certifications attest by a qualified third party, that requirements, for example relating to services and infrastructures, have been met. These requirements are defined or set out in the respective certification system, together with the granting rules of the certification body, such as the conditions for participation, the individual steps in the certification process or the form of the certificate (Putnings 2018, 255–256).

Badges, awards and prizes are, like certificates, promotional symbols that the defined requirements of the awarding body and its

stakeholders have been met; in addition, the award increases awareness of, and trust in, the services and the open materials made available. This in turn can have a positive effect in terms of increased usage. Winners of badges, awards or prizes can raise their profile with their funding bodies, which may provide advantages when competing for funding. The application for such badges, awards or prizes is usually preceded by a self-evaluation, including review, documentation and, if necessary, optimisation. This leads to process-inherent quality improvements prior to participation. Winning a badge, award or prize is also an achievement that boosts staff motivation; in this context, it can also be beneficial for staff recruitment if the award and commitment to new library roles, such as open science, are used to promote the library (Putnings 2018, 252–253).

Badges, awards and prizes, similar to certifications, are therefore an essential part of good quality communication as part of (information) marketing (Putnings 2018, 259).

Limitation of the Scope

The scope of the following chapter is limited to the geographical reference of the contributing authors (Germany) and accordingly to open science badges, awards and prizes relevant to Germany and its scientific community. In view of the international impact of SDGs, an extension of the scope to the European or international level is recommended for further analysis.

With reference to Germany, a certain diversity of badges, awards and prizes with different characteristics can be observed. In terms of content, these range from open science, open access and open data to open educational resources, and in terms of scale from international, national and regional to institutional competitions.

The following selection is intended to show the most important open science badges, awards and prizes for Germany and, at the same time, to take into account the diversity of the activities. For this reason, badges, awards and prizes open only to the institution and its members or restricted to certain Bundesländer/Federal States are also presented with selected examples.

Badges, awards and prizes that no longer take place, like the German open data Impact Award (<https://www.stifterverband.org/innosci/open-data-impact-award>) or that are largely outside the sphere of influence, responsibility or participation of libraries or librarians are not taken into account. This exclusion applies in particular to open science badges, which are

used by commercial publishers and journals in their articles to prove the open science methods of their authors and thus increase the trustworthiness of the articles.

Certifications, such as the DINI Certificate for open access Repositories and Publication Services, are also excluded. Detailed information on this can be found in Putnings 2018.

Open Science Badges, Awards, and Prizes Relevant to Germany

The following tables provide structured overviews of the selected badges, awards and prizes, taking into account the aforementioned scope.

Examples of Recurring Open Science Badges, Awards and Prizes Relevant to Libraries

Homepage	https://yerun.eu/2023/11/yerun-open-science-awards-2023-now-open-apply-by-5-december/ (Call for 2023).
Criteria	See PDF of the call at the link above and the open science objectives mentioned there, as well as <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Description: What is the open science practice/initiative about and what are its key open science objectives? ● Outputs: What has the initiative achieved so far? ● Reusability: What steps have been taken for others to reuse this initiative? ● Follow-up: How do you intend to use the award?
Organiser	Young European Research Universities Network (YERUN). Only researchers or administrative or professional support staff members from one of the YERUN universities can apply (https://yerun.eu/about-us/); in Germany, these are currently the universities of Klagenfurt, Potsdam, Ulm, Konstanz, and Bremen. The

	YERUN Secretary General may be contacted to questions: secretarygeneral@yerun.eu .
Badge, award or prize character	Competitive character (up to five initiatives will be awarded), material incentive of a total of €2,000 for each award.
Application process	There is an annual call for applications. The online application form (https://openscience2023.yerun.eu/ for 2023) should then be filled out with a description of the open science practice/initiative and relevant points regarding the criteria. The evaluation after the application deadline will be carried out in two phases by an evaluation panel with representatives from YERUN institutions, and the winners will be announced within two months of the end of the call. The awards will be celebrated in a festive YERUN Open Science Awards Ceremony. As part of this ceremony, the open practices are presented as best practices.
Example badge, award or prize winners	The award winners are presented in the ceremony and in subsequent “Congratulations to the winners” announcements. See for example https://yerun.eu/news-events/ , tag filter on open science. In 2022, for example, one winner was the research-based digital “Theodor Fontane Archive” from the University of Potsdam because of their long-term digital strategy for open access to cultural data and cultural heritage.
Special aspects relating to libraries as drivers of education and/or SDGs	The award criteria <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Making the output of research, including publications, data, software, and other research materials freely accessible. ● Making scientific research more reproducible by increasing the amount and quality of published information that is necessary to reproduce research results.

	<p>and some others contribute to SDG 16.10, to ensure public access to information and SDG 4 quality education is supported by the award criteria</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Raising awareness of open science for example through events, programmes, educational and training tools. <p>SDG 17, like 17.6 to enhance international cooperation on and access to science, technology and innovation is conceptually part of the criteria</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Using open collaborative methods and tools to increase efficiency and widen participation in research.
Additional information	<p>The festive YERUN Open Science Awards Ceremony often also includes political and awareness-raising speeches on open science, most recently in 2023, for example, the lecture “What’s next for open science in Europe?” by the Deputy Head of Unit on Open Science of the European Commission.</p>

Table 1: YERUN Open Science Awards.

Homepage	<p>https://awards.oeglobal.org/</p>
Criteria	<p>The OE Awards are usually divided into four main areas (Individuals or People, Open Assets, Open Practices, and Special Awards – the latter includes, for example, the Diversity, Equity & Inclusion Award) with several sub-categories. In 2023, there were four subcategories each (https://awards.oeglobal.org/about/2023-explorer/).</p> <p>The criteria for the award are rather vaguely described. The overall aim of the OE Awards Review Committee is to identify and recognise the best examples of excellence and outstanding contributions to the international open education community, in the form of distin-</p>

	<p>guished leaders (Individuals or People category) and distinctive open educational resources or open practices & initiatives (Open Assets, Open Practices, and Special Awards categories) based on the applications.</p>
Organiser	<p>The OE Awards are hosted by Open Education Global (OEG), a global, members based, non-profit organisation. Contact and information in case of questions is available at awards@oeglobal.org.</p>
Badge, award or prize character	<p>Competitive character, no material incentive.</p>
Application process	<p>The nomination process is described in an Awards Nomination Guide (see for example https://awards.oeglobal.org/about/2023-guide/ for the year 2023). It describes who can nominate, which award to nominate (depending on category and sub-category), and what information is required. The relevant nomination form templates (available online) must be completed during the annual “Call for Nominations”. There is one template for Individual Awards and one for Open Assets, Open Practices and Special Awards.</p> <p>Each form in the Open Assets, Open Practices and Special Awards categories must include a narrative explaining why the resource, tool or practice is useful and how it impacts open supporters and advocates. This narrative should be accompanied by, for example, video testimonials and any additional supporting material or notes that the OE Awards Review Committee should be aware of.</p> <p>In the case of the Individual Awards’, details of the nominees, their motivation, a letter of support from colleagues, a video testimonial and any additional material or notes should be included. These should provide an overall picture of the nominee’s achievements in openness.</p>

	<p>The submissions are then assessed by the OEAWards Review Committee. The finalists as well as the winners will be announced online (for example via YouTube stream), and further presentations and honours take place at the annual OEG conference.</p>
<p>Example badge, award or prize winners</p>	<p>The OEAWards winners are presented in the Hall of Fame. For Germany, for example, see https://awards.oeglobal.org/awards/?sfm_country=Germany.</p>
<p>Special aspects relating to libraries as drivers of education and/or SDGs</p>	<p>In 2023, the individual awards were themed “People in open” and were presented in four sub-categories: Leadership, Educator, Catalyst and Student. The Educator Award, for example, recognises open practices in teaching. The Leadership Award honours contributions to promoting the open education movement with a national and/or global impact. The Catalyst Award acknowledges individuals who are committed to the creation and implementation of OER and the application of open practices. The Student Award is given to students who have championed or benefited academically from the re-use of open educational resources or open educational practices. All categories thus recognise achievements that contribute to SDG 4 quality education as well as SDG 16, especially 16.10 to ensure public access to information.</p> <p>The same applies to the award categories</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Open Assets, i.e. open education initiatives that produce materials with educational purpose and value (subcategories: Significant impact OER, Open Curation, Open Reuse, Open Infrastructure) and ● Open Practices (subcategories: Open Pedagogy, Open Collaboration, Open Research, Open Policy). <p>The Special Awards on the one hand make specific reference to the SDGs, with the “Enacting SDG</p>

	<p>Award” recognising the application of open practices in the area of SDG target fulfilment. On the other hand, the “Diversity, Equity & Inclusion Award” contributes to SDG 5, Gender Equality and SDG 10, Reduced inequalities, especially 10.2 to empower and promote the inclusion of all. The “Open Resilience Award” picks up on exemplary open educational practices to address challenges arising in crisis and therefore plays a role in the SDGs 1, 2, 3, 6, 13 and many more.</p>
Additional information	<p>The great strength of the awards lies in their international reputation and the extensive celebration of the awards in several stages. Another advantage is that there are several awards in different categories, so that almost all players in the open science and open education community can find opportunities to apply, as long as they can demonstrate excellence and exciting projects.</p> <p>A disadvantage is that the award criteria are relatively vague and non-transparent, so there is no publicly available information on what the award decisions are clearly based on.</p>

Table 2: Open Education Awards for Excellence (OE Awards).

Homepage	https://badge.openbiblio.eu (in German only)
Criteria	https://badge.openbiblio.eu/kriterien/ (in German only, unofficial English translation is available at https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7689138)
Organiser	The Open Library Badge project was initiated by Gerald Jagusch. A working group consisting of a group of volunteers from the library sector who are committed to openness is responsible for reviewing applications and awarding the badge. The working group can be contacted at: badge@openbiblio.eu .

Badge, award or prize character	No competitive character, no material incentive.
Application process	The 15 defined criteria are explained and queried via the https://badge.openbiblio.eu/bewerbung/ online form (in German only). Proof of how the answers can be verified is requested, for example by providing URLs, with a brief explanation if necessary. Libraries wishing to receive the badge should meet at least 5 of the 15 criteria. Applications are reviewed by the Open Library Badge team. They guarantee a confidential review, no rankings or comparisons, and a quick award of the badge, which can be used to promote the library and easily posted on the library's website and social networks.
Example badge, award or prize winners	The badge holders are listed at https://badge.openbiblio.eu/badge-traegerinnen/ and vice versa with their best practices at https://badge.openbiblio.eu/best-practices/ (both pages in German only).
Special aspects relating to libraries as drivers of education and/or SDGs	<p>The following badge criteria contribute to SDG 10 and in particular to 10.2 by promoting the inclusion of people with disabilities:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Usability for all. Making your own website accessible ● Library as an open place. The library offers a course programme for integration, inclusion, and/or emancipation to promote equal access for all. <p>SDG 16, especially 16.10 to ensure public access to information, as well as SDG 4 quality education is supported by the badge criteria</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Professional development opportunities. Offering internal and external information and

	<p>training opportunities</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">● Make open access resources visible. Integrate open access sources into local search systems and contribute to the better indexing of open access resources.● Reveal open access potentials. The library supports the identification of open access potentials through advice in the field of open science and open educational resource● Teaching and learning materials under open licence. Provide the library's teaching and learning materials for reuse and editing● Integration of own and external users. In fulfilling its function as a service provider or within professional/regional networks, the library provides expertise and existing infrastructure for its own as well as external use● Support open knowledge communities. Organise community events in collaboration with Wikimedia or other knowledge communities or participate in projects to improve Wikipedia or Wikidata● Always publish open access in the library as well. Library staff members publish in open access. <p>With the criterion</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">● Enable text and data mining. The library allows its users to perform text and data mining on their own and licensed collections. In licence agreements, it generally negotiates the right to text and data mining and it informs users accordingly <p>SDG 9 industry, innovation and infrastructure, is also facilitated, as text and data mining are important aspects for innovations in areas such as artificial intelligence.</p>
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Additional information	The badge is intended to publicise relevant activities and services offered by libraries in the broader field of open science and openness. It is aimed at both public and academic libraries. With its broad coverage and understanding of openness, the Open Library Badge initiative is one of the most interesting initiatives in Germany.
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Table 3: Open Library Badge.

Homepage	https://enter-award.irights-lab.de (in German only)
Criteria	https://enter-award.irights-lab.de/bewerben/ (in German only): There are five award categories (infrastructure, skills transfer, young talent, pioneering work and cooperation) and the main criteria that are queried are: What has been achieved with regard to the respective category? What is the motivation behind it? What is unique about it? How does the submission contribute to sustainability? What impact does it have? How does it promote inclusivity?
Organiser	<i>Enter – Der Open-Access-Award</i> as a project was initiated by iRights.Lab and is supported by the Federal Ministry of Education and Research (Bundesministerium für Bildung und Forschung, BMBF) in Germany. The members of the jury are presented at https://enter-award.irights-lab.de/jury/ (in German only). The winners will be selected in a multi-stage process involving the organisers (longlist) and the jury (shortlist, winners). The project team at iRights.Lab can be contacted at: openaccessaward@irights-lab.de
Badge, award or prize character	The award has a competitive character. One winner will be chosen in each of the categories. The winners of each category will receive prize money of a total of €1,000. The prizes will be awarded at a festive awards

	ceremony.
Application process	<p>The detailed conditions of participation and questions about the criteria can be found at https://badge.openbiblio.eu/bewerbung/ (in German only). Anyone who is committed to the idea of Open Access can apply: Academics, research institutions, libraries, museums, archives, repositories, advice centres, publishers and other dedicated persons. Participation is only possible in one category.</p> <p>There is a form on the website that must be completed for the application. It can be previewed at https://enter-award.irights-lab.de/wp-content/uploads/2024/02/Bewerbungsformular_Enter-Award_Ansicht.pdf. There is also the opportunity to propose others for the award via email.</p>
Example badge, award or prize winners	The prize has just been implemented and is being awarded for the first time, so there are no winners yet.
Special aspects relating to libraries as drivers of education and/or SDGs	<p>With regard to the objective of the award mentioned below, the goal of a cultural shift towards free knowledge for the general public contributes to SDG 16.10 to ensure public access to information.</p> <p>Each contribution must explicitly state how it relates to sustainability and inclusion. The category of skills transfer (“Kompetenzvermittlung” in German) is also a driving force for high-quality ESD/SDG education.</p>

Additional information	<p>The award will be presented for the first time in 2024 and aims to spread the culture of free knowledge to the general public. The publication of scientific research papers or results in accordance with open access principles is to become much more the norm and the benefits of this should be better emphasised. This will be achieved by publicising best practices to a wider audience throughout Germany. In addition, organisations such as libraries and individuals will also receive recognition for their pioneering roles and their commitment in the field.</p> <p>Due to the early stages of the project, some details might be subject to change.</p>
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Table 4: Enter – Der Open-Access-Award.

Further Examples that Could also Serve as Models

Of course, prizes can also be awarded at institutional level to members of the institution. In this way, open access can be made more visible and open science plans and projects at the institution can be promoted. The Humboldt University of Berlin's Open Access Award is presented below as an example.

Homepage	https://www.ub.hu-berlin.de/en/researching-and-publishing/open-access/open-access-award?set_language=en
Criteria	See link above, page section “Award criteria”
Organiser	<p>In 2023, the award jury was made up of the Humboldt University's Open Access Representative and Director of the University Library, the Open Access Officer at the University Library, the Head of the Research Service Centre and a Professor of Information Retrieval at the Institute of Library and Information Science and Chair of the Academic Senate's Media Commission. The award appears to be organised by the Open Access</p>

	Team of the University Library; it can be contacted at: openaccess@ub.hu-berlin.de .
Badge, award or prize character	Competitive character, material incentive of a total of €5,000.
Application process	There is a call for applications. This takes place annually at the end of the year and is usually open until the beginning of the following year. The award always relates to open access achievements from the current or previous year. The applications with the described achievements are reviewed and assessed by the award jury. The award is celebrated at a major ceremony in autumn or at the end of the year.
Example badge, award or prize winners	The award holders are listed at the homepage, page section “Laureates”.
Special aspects relating to libraries as drivers of education and/or SDGs	<p>The award criteria</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● a special commitment or engagement for open access publishing or in making publications freely accessible ● the successful carrying-out of a project or the creation of a product with the aim of implementing and strengthening open access or ● a special commitment to communicating and transferring open access and its principles to the public, the scientific community or the wider community of a field/discipline <p>refers to SDG 16 and the latter point also to SDG 4.</p> <p>One of the last prizewinners, a team from the Fundamental Rights Project of the OpenRewi initiative (https://openrewi.org/en/), won for example the award</p>

	with a project to create an open access textbook on fundamental rights in an open and collaborative writing process with a total of 23 authors. This fits well to SDG 16.10 to ensure public access to information and protect fundamental freedoms.
Additional information	Unlike the Open Library Badge, for example, this is a competition and usually only one person receives the award. However, the award may be split into two individual awards if there are two outstanding and equally deserving achievements among the applications, which are either of a completely different nature or which should be fairly distinguished.

Table 5: Humboldt-Universität zu Berlin's Open Access Award as an example of an internal institutional award.

There are also prizes whose annual calls and aspects to be rewarded are based on changing scientific topics. This means that there is not always a connection to open science; other current topics such as artificial intelligence could also be the focus of an award. An example is the Brandenburger Landeslehrpreis 2023, which had a one-off focus on open educational resources.

Homepage	https://mwfk.brandenburg.de/mwfk/de/wissenschaft/brandenburger-wissenschaftspreis/landeslehrpreis/~mais2redc623161de (in German only)
Criteria	<p>Teachers at Brandenburg's universities were honoured for their outstanding open educational resources. These could already be freely available or unpublished concepts.</p> <p>Definition of OER according to the call for proposals: open educational resources are educational materials that are published under an open licence and can be used, stored, processed, modified and (re)distributed by anyone free of charge. OER can be, for example, individual media, complete courses, textbooks, teaching concepts, scripts, streaming videos, multimedia applications or podcasts.</p> <p>The proposals were evaluated on the basis of the following key questions:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Which target group should the OER address?

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● What are the learning objectives of the OER? ● What competencies should be acquired in the course in which the OER are or will be used? ● What is the didactic approach of the OER? ● To what extent does the material help learners to engage interactively with the content? ● How is the material made accessible to people with disabilities? ● To what extent can parts of the OER be used in a flexible way? ● Which considerations are decisive for the choice of OER platform and licence? ● In the case of previously unpublished OER concepts: What is the planned timetable for publication?
<p>Organiser</p>	<p>The prize was awarded by the Brandenburg Ministry of Science, Research and Culture.</p> <p>The decision to award the prizes was made by a jury, consisting of the previous year's winners, two Vice-Presidents for Studies and Teaching, a representative of the Ministry, as well as representatives of the “<i>Studienqualität Brandenburg</i>” network and student representatives. Proposals were judged anonymously.</p>
<p>Badge, award or prize character</p>	<p>Competitive character, material incentive. Three prizes of €10,000 each.</p>
<p>Application process</p>	<p>There was a call for proposals until June 2023. Proposals could be submitted using a special form at landeslehrpreis@mwfk.brandenburg.de. In addition to information on the proposed teacher and course, the form also asked for information on the key questions above. The anonymised entries were evaluated by the jury.</p> <p>The departmental and faculty councils as well as the central institutions for teaching, further education and language and the general students committee of the state universities in Brandenburg were entitled to submit nominations through their respective chairpersons or management. Each organisational unit could submit a maximum of two proposals for lecturers to be honoured.</p>

<p>Example badge, award or prize winners</p>	<p>The award holders 2023 are listed at the homepage, page section “Landeslehrpreis 2023”. One of the three winners of the 23 proposals was the certificate course in research data management for students, a joint project of three universities in Brandenburg.</p> <p>The course was developed as part of a larger collaborative project and is in the responsibility of the Brandenburg state initiative for research data management. It took place for the first time in March 2023 with students from Brandenburg's universities and was conducted as a one-week online spring school. The certificate course, which is held at least once a year, provides basic knowledge of research data management to enable participants to manage research data in a sustainable way and promotes the application of international standards of good scientific practice in research data management. The content is delivered by lecturers from various professional areas at the three cooperating universities, including the library.</p> <p>All course materials have been published as OER in a freely accessible format on the research data repository Zenodo. See https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7936966.</p>
<p>Special aspects relating to libraries as drivers of education and/or SDGs</p>	<p>OER support the global sustainable development goal SDG 4 of enabling inclusive, equitable and quality education for all. The closeness to the principles of OER is particularly evident in the specific goals for the education sector mentioned there. OER can play an important role as a driver of social innovation through education.</p>
<p>Additional information</p>	<p>The state teaching award honours excellent university teaching in Brandenburg. The theme of the competition changes every year; it was held for the eleventh time in 2023. The 2023 award ceremony took place in November 2023 in Potsdam. The current call for entries for the <i>Landeslehrpreis 2024</i> has the motto “Artificial intelligence in university teaching”.</p>

Table 6: *Brandenburger Landeslehrpreis 2023* under the motto ‘Open educational resources in Higher Education’ as an example of a federal state award which had the topic of OER only once.

Conclusion

Our work started by contextualising open science, the SDGs, the ESD programme, the role of libraries, and the topic of badges, awards and prizes in the scope of the book. The focus was on the topic of library roles in transforming the learning environment for sustainable development and promoting open science: at least 10 of the 17 SDGs require ongoing scientific input and in order to achieve these goals on a global scale, it is therefore essential to make research results and other educational resources openly accessible and disseminate them without restrictions to the intended stakeholders (UNESCO 2021a).

As IFLA states on this topic, “Libraries have long been key players in advancing open science and development, and today in particular are playing a key role in ensuring that the two come together for the benefit of all” (IFLA 2024). The activities and potential of libraries are however often overlooked and need to be strengthened (Hauke 2023, 86; IFLA 2024).

One marketing activity to change this can be badges, awards and prizes, such as the Open Library Badge in Germany as a high-profile honour. The other awards and prizes presented in our work reflect a certain range, for example in terms of regional coverage and visibility (international, federal state-specific, institutional), as well as different aspects of open science or openness, and which SDGs they support with their criteria to be fulfilled and awarded; they are selected from a German perspective.

Effects of Badges, Awards and Prizes

With regard to the above-mentioned range, each badge, award or prize has the potential/effect, at its respective level and beyond, to raise awareness for open practices in science, to draw attention to best practices and thus to establish open standards, in addition to providing financial support and appreciation, where applicable.

Effective marketing methods are utilised by organising, for example, prestigious award ceremonies, highlighting exemplary champions, publishing press releases and overviews of previous winners. This promotes projects that create or foster open access resources, and imitation effects will lead to a multiplier effect.

One focus that has not been explored in detail in this work is the motives of, and effects on, the individual open science prizewinners. Reference can be made to the PhD project of Ronny Röwert,

who conducted research on this topic (see Figure 2, based on Rowert 2024, 160): in the context of this chapter, for example, it is interesting to see that, in addition to expected incentives such as citation and reuse of the prize-winning research, benefits for society and meaningfulness also play a large role.

Recommendations

It was found that libraries did not play a direct role in all of the relevant badges, awards or prizes in terms of the mentioned awarding organisation, the applicants approached and/or the potential winners.

In all of them, however, they provide essential background support for science by making existing knowledge accessible and by offering advice and infrastructure for open science. Their traditional proximity to researchers is an advantage in driving cultural change. However, libraries could play an even more active role by offering such prizes alone or jointly, or by becoming more actively involved in their organisation.

For organisers who already bestow badges, awards and prizes, it would be advisable to make a stronger and more explicit reference to the SDGs than has been the case so far. The OE Awards “Special awards” such as the Enacting SDG Award, the Diversity, Equity & Inclusion Award and the Open Resilience Award are examples worth emulating here.

With regard to the two different characters of the badges, awards and prizes (competitive or non-competitive), it is recommended to use the best of both worlds. Non-competitive application procedures with extensive transparent criteria, based on the fulfillment that anyone can achieve recognition, are almost a quality certificate (for example in the same way as ISO 9001 for quality management), as described in the section on the relationship to certifications. However, it is only major celebratory ceremonies that create the appropriate publicity and recognition. This is usually more the case in competitive procedures, as “the best” are then honoured. However, both could be combined: the use of a transparent catalogue of criteria and the regular celebration of the award winners.

The prize money seems to be of secondary importance. If awarded, it should be a “real” reward: organisations active in open science are likely to have an open access publishing fund anyway; the prize money should therefore not be earmarked for the payment of open access article-processing charges.

Finally, we would like to point out the importance of making best practice visible. The Open Library Badge can be credited here, as it lists not only the badge holders, but also their best practices, such as projects or activities through which the criteria are met. This could even be extended in terms of replicability, for example through detailed descriptions of who was involved and what (open source) tools and methods were used. As mentioned earlier, imitation could lead to multiplication of activities.

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